

Variational Principle, Conserved Quantity and Stability

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In physics there exist a number of variational principles such as the Lagrangian approach, Fermat's least time principle for light/ Maupertuis' variational principle for particles and the maximization of entropy subject to a constraint. These approaches are associated with global type solutions and appear as independent approaches. For example, the Lagrangian approach considers various paths from the same initial and final points and chooses the one which extremizes the action: $\int dt L$. Fermat's principle is associated with various different paths from a starting point to an endpoint and chooses the one associated with least overall (global) time. Entropy is proportional to the \ln of all arrangements and so one thinks of globally maximizing these.

Thus taken independently the focus of variational principles is to choose an extreme solution from a large number of possible solutions which immediately begs the question: How does the system (nature) evaluate all of these different paths/possibilities?

In (1) we suggested that the above variational principles may be associated with underlying local conservation laws. For example, for the Lagrangian case there is an associated conservation of energy. Thus $v(x)$ must change locally so that $.5mv(x)v(x) + V(x) = E$. For Fermat's principle there is conservation of momentum in the x direction (if the mirror or medium surface also lies in this direction). Thus light may move locally such that its (p_x) remains constant. (p_y) only changes abruptly when there is an interface change or mirror in its direction. Mathematically one may construct the above variational principles from the given conservation laws. As a result, there is no reason to necessarily consider a variational principle independently of its locally conserved quantity as argued in (1). In other words, one does not need to consider many different paths. Conservation leads locally to a single path.

In this note we ask: If conservation leads locally to a solution, why consider a variational principle at all? Is it simply a convenient computational tool? We argue that there seems to be the idea of stable equilibrium present. In classical mechanics one has the notion of a stable equilibrium (static problem) which is associated with extremization. This is often associated with a stationary object which when slightly perturbed undergoes periodic motion. Here we argue that dynamical systems such as a Lagrangian system, or light or gas particles may also be seen as being in a stable equilibrium if one considers a variational principle together with its conserved quantity. The conserved quantity (p_x or E etc) characterizes the equilibrium while the variational principle shows that this is a stable equilibrium, even if light or a particle is traveling and interacting in space.

Variational Principle Standing Alone

Variational principles are often presented as standalone approaches. Such is the case for the Lagrangian formalism, Fermat's principle and the maximization of entropy subject to a constant energy. These principles are presented as choosing a unique solution out of a large number of possible solutions such that the solution extremizes a certain value. For example the Lagrangian problem extremizes the action $\int dt L$ and Fermat's principle extremizes

overall time. Presented in this way the following question immediately arises: How does nature know how to test all of the possible solutions and then choose the extreme one?

If one examines the exact process in which extremization is performed, however, say for Fermat's principle, one sees that a general expression is written representing all possible two ray paths from the same initial point to the same final characterized by one variable. This variable represents an invariant spatial variable. For the case of a mirror or medium in the x direction at $y=0$, there is a constraint in the y direction so only x is free. The extremization process is written in terms of x and then d/dx is applied to $t_1(x) + t_2(x)$ such that:

$$d/dx (t_1+t_2) = 0 \quad ((1))$$

Thus even though each different x value represents a different path, one is not really testing many paths. One is simply stating that the correct solution (i.e. x value) is one for which slight deviations i.e. d/dx lead to $d/dx (t_1+t_2) = 0$. In other words the correct solution represents a stable equilibrium. To see that one is not really sampling many paths, one may note that for Fermat's principle, for example, ((1)) is equivalent to a conservation equation, namely conservation of momentum in the x direction. Thus a stable solution is immediately linked to local conservation. This enhances the idea that one does not need to sample various paths - the correct path is one which locally conserves (px) and this solution is stable.

For a Lagrangian the conserved quantity is energy E from $.5mv(x)v(x) + V(x) = E$. In (1) we showed how taking d/dx is like varying the solution $x(t)$ slightly. Thus local conservation of energy directs the local motion, but the variational Lagrangian approach shows that this solution is stable to slight perturbations.

Thus a conservation law and its corresponding variational principle are intertwined. The conservation law shows locally how a particle may move from one point to another, but the variational principle shows how this motion is stable.

Stable Equilibrium

The notion of equilibrium is usually applied to static problems in mechanics or thermodynamics such as a Maxwell-Boltzmann gas. In other words there does not seem to be overall motion or changes in averages in time in these problems. A static particle (whether inside a curved surface or hanging from a string) does not move. If perturbed slightly it undergoes periodic motion about the static solution. This motion is described by a variational condition such that d/dx leads to zero, thus expanding a potential $V(x)$, the first order term is 0 and the remaining xx term describes an oscillator. In the case of equilibrium in a gas, the overall properties of the gas do not change in time on average.

We argue that a static position or a lack of change in time is linked to conservation. For example a static object is at a point $x=a$ $y=b$ and oscillations occur about this point. $x=a$ and $y=b$ represent a conserved point. Thus the idea of stable equilibrium may be applied to other conserved quantities even if there is overall motion in the system. For example, in the case of Fermat's least time principle there is overall motion of light, but there is also a conserved quantity namely momentum in the direction of an invariant variable. Because this variable is invariant one may change it slightly i.e. take d/dx of a function such that $d/dx G(x) = 0$. This is of

the form of variational principle and describes stable equilibrium. Thus there may be overall motion in keeping with the conserved quantity with slight deviations leading, say in x , to a stability equation i.e. extremization $dG(x)/dx = 0$.

In the case of Lagrangian motion, conservation of energy describes the overall motion. This is a local condition with E energy governing the equilibrium. Taking d/dx may be seen as perturbing this motion i.e. $.5mv(x)v(x) + V(x) = E$ and for given time t , x and $x+dx$ represent different solutions. The correct one is x so the deviation $d/dx (.5mvv+V(x)) = 0$. This leads to: $d/dt \partial L/\partial v - \partial L/\partial x = 0$ which extremizes the action $\text{Integral } L dt$. For a free particle, we showed how the action is directly linked to both conservation of energy and momentum for perturbations in t and x .

Thus the idea of stable equilibrium seems to apply to more than static mechanical problems and the equilibrium of a gas. We argue that it may also be seen in overall motion as in the case of light and particles described by a Lagrangian.

Conclusion

In conclusion we argue that there exist a number of variational principles associated with the extremization of a particular global quantity. For Fermat's principle, this global quantity is the overall time in a reflection/refraction problem for example. For a Lagrangian system it is the action $\text{Integral } dt L$ where $L=T-V$ (usually). Thus if considered alone, a variational principle suggests that many possible solutions are tested and only the stationary one is chosen. This immediately leads to the question: How does nature test the various solutions? We suggested in (1) that different solutions need not be tested because the above variational principles are associated with local conservation laws. In Fermat's case this is conservation of momentum in the direction of an invariant spatial variable, say x , if a mirror or medium lies in the x direction at $y=b$. For a Lagrangian system it is energy E . Thus the solution path is governed by this locally conserved quantity yet there is stability in this solution governed by the fact that it is a stationary solution i.e. the variational principle.

Thus we suggest that variational principles should be considered together with locally conserved quantities. (One may be derived from the other so they are intertwined.)

The conservation law shows how light or a particle may move from one point to the next, but the variational principle shows how this motion is stable to perturbations i.e how the system, even though moving overall, may be in equilibrium. Thus the notion of equilibrium extends beyond the idea of statics or equilibrium gases/thermodynamics.

References

1. Ruggeri, Francesco R Stationary Path in a Lagrangian and Energy Conservation (preprint, zenodo, 2022)